

USING THE PROBLEM TEACHING METHOD IN MUSIC EDUCATION

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Annotation: today, scientific research activities and research in this field are carried out to increase the effectiveness of music education. This article discusses the theoretical foundations of using problem-based teaching technologies in music education.

Key words: Music education, problem situation, technology, group work, interactive teaching, "Aquarium" method, "Muzyorar" method.

Introduction:

Today, in our free and prosperous, independent country, comprehensive updates and positive changes are being carried out in the education system as well as in all areas.

Such changes and updates are also taking place in the field of music and art. Including art and music schools, pre-school education for gifted children and children with a high interest in the art of music, in order to ensure that the young generation will grow into a highly cultured, aesthetically developed, mature, educated, well-rounded generation in all respects. In institutions, various youth centers named Barkamol Avlod are being built.

In the implementation of the "National Personnel Training Program", the fundamental reconstruction of the education system, that is, the consideration of the basic rules of the development of public education and the understanding of the essence of the necessity of modern educational technologies for the development of the society, current in all areas of education issues related to acquisition and mastering are one of the urgent problems of modern pedagogy.

Issues aimed at the development of musical art are also indicated in the Action Strategy project on the five priority areas of further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, developed by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev.

Improving the effectiveness of teaching based on the introduction of modern pedagogical technologies into the educational process, as a demand of the times, puts a great responsibility on the music teacher, among all pedagogical teachers. In the process of teaching any subject, including music culture lessons. It is the teacher who is activated, who creates an opportunity for students to be active participants of the lesson, independent thinkers, observers, and able to express their opinions. The teacher determines the conditions for their use together with the teaching methods, ways, forms, tools that are convenient and interesting for him and the students, and tries to increase the efficiency of the educational process with the help of advanced pedagogical technologies. Therefore, innovative pedagogical technology, educational technologies are considered as the most effective tools in the educational process. Today, they are widely used in the practice of world pedagogy.

The technological approach to education is one of the factors that actively influence the pedagogical process and determine its effectiveness, integrity and success.

Teaching through interactive methods and communicative teaching is a resource of standard teaching. As a result of using the method of teaching and working in small groups, it is possible to speed up the teaching process, that is, to raise the development potential to a high level, and create conditions for deep and extensive learning of the content of the training. Not all active learning methods are interactive. When we talk about interactive teaching methods, first of all, it is necessary to understand the method of studying and mastering the subject among students, which enhances the process of interaction and teaching from the point of psychological mechanism. Among them, the first example is working in small groups. There are many reasons why small group work methods are underused in today's teaching process, including the predominance of old-fashioned methods of explanation, demonstration and illustration, and new, innovative, communication-based methods. Lack of confidence in teaching methods. In addition, teachers themselves do not know interactive teaching methods, lack of methodical training is the reason why these methods are not widespread.

In addition, today, the application of interactive teaching methods in medical universities is one of the urgent problems. Their correct application to the teaching process can raise the educational process to a higher level, and in the future, it is necessary to bring the teacher of general practice closer to the real life situation, in which he should acquire scientific thinking and professional skills based on the state standard. .

Purpose and issues of interactive teaching methods.

The main essence of interactive teaching methods is that all students involved in the course of the lesson understand their own knowledge and thoughts while studying and mastering them through discussion. One of the main requirements is unity, joint thinking, and joint activities among students in the process of studying the curriculum, each student can share his opinion, innovation, knowledge and propose a solution to the problem. is done through . The main issues of using the teaching process in the interactive mode at the department of general surgery are:

- raising the interest of students in the process of learning music;
- bringing the teaching process closer to the real conditions of the teacher's life;
- effective communication methods, i.e. proper formation of teacher-student and mutual communication skills;
- raising the process of mastering new theoretical knowledge and practical skills to a new level;
- increasing students' responsibility for the educational process.

When using interactive methods, the student becomes the main member of the learning process of the group lesson, and his fundamental knowledge is considered the basis of the learning center. The teacher, in turn, does not give new, ready-made knowledge to students, but increases mastery by developing the process of independent research and thinking among most students. The difference of interactive methods from traditional teaching methods is that it changes the process of interaction between the teacher and the student: the activity of the student prevails over the activity of the teacher, which, in turn, is the main goal of the teacher and contributes to the initiative thinking process of students. will create high-level conditions. The teacher is mainly responsible for the general issues of organizing the lesson process, preparation of necessary assignments, formulating questions and topics for

communication among students, giving consultations, controlling the process of implementation of time and planning stages. Interactive methods:

- increases students' interest;
- at the same time, the group actively involves all students in the lesson process;
- increases the result of using any reading materials;
- increases the efficiency of active learning of the curriculum;
- provides feedback;
- forms and increases the ratio of independent thought and knowledge among students;
- accelerates practical skills;
- improves interpersonal communication skills;
- causes a change in behavior.

The main rules for organizing the interactive learning process:

- It is necessary to involve all students in the learning process. For this, it is necessary to use modernized technologies that involve all students in the learning process.

- It is necessary to create conditions for the implementation of one's own opinion, to positively evaluate students who actively participate and have the right actions.

- It is necessary to ensure the conditions of the educational auditorium in such a way that students can easily change their places and move to work in small and large groups.

- Accurately link all treatments and timelines. It is necessary not to break the rules, having agreed on this at the beginning of the lesson. For example: all students should be tolerant of all the speech and opinion of their peers, everyone should be able to speak freely and be respected.

Mandatory conditions for organizing interactive training methods:

- A reliable and positive relationship between the teacher and the student;
- Mutual reflection during the discussion between the teacher and the student.
- Including vivid examples and evidence in the educational process.
- Multifaceted data, types of activities, their mobility.
- Inclusion of external and internal motivation of activity and interest of students.

Preference of interactive teaching methods:

1. increase interest activity and motivation among students.
2. to increase the responsibility and independence of students in relation to the results of teaching activities.

3. Students acquire new knowledge and skills.

4. students' ability to master practical skills and be ready to use them.

5. forming a respectful attitude towards colleagues and others.

A special field of psychology - youth psychology - deals with the study of the general features of a person's age. In its most general form, age stages such as school age, adolescence and social maturity are distinguished. On this basis, it is possible to indicate the following age periods and educational institutions according to them:

The main topics of the general foundations of musical pedagogy section are the musical development, education and formation of the personality. The musical development of a person is manifested as the process of formation and formation of his musical abilities and musical culture. Musical development is a comprehensive improvement of innate and acquired quantitative and qualitative changes in the physical, mental and spiritual

development of a person's musical culture. A person goes through several stages in his musical development.

"Circle" method

Students sit in a circle and perform various exercises. The advantage of this method, compared to the method of passing students in rows, is that no student feels that he is separated, that is, someone is behind and someone is ahead. Not every student is left out of the educator's eyes and attention.

Everyone feels "equal".

"Aquarium" method

In this method, several students perform different tasks in a circle. These pupils in the middle are like fish in the aquarium. Their every move is closely watched by students sitting around the circle.

The "negotiation" method

Purpose: To create a free environment for participants to get to know each other. "Muzyoralar" are called different acquaintances. In short, this activity helps students behave, get to know each other and create an atmosphere of mutual trust in the group. He invites them to participate and support each other. In the process of education, we can create new types of such exercises.

"Grouping" method

In this way, students learn to work together in the process of completing various tasks, and the student who mastered it well learns to work together with the students who master it poorly. In the course of the training, it becomes necessary to divide students into small groups when performing a task. Then they can be divided into groups in different ways. For example: a simple way of dividing into groups is that the students sitting around the first two-seater table face the students sitting around the second table, and the students around the third table face the fourth table they sit looking at the students. Thus, students are divided into several groups.

Another method of grouping: the teacher asks the students to name several (depending on how many groups the teacher wants the students to be divided into) several pets. Then he names each student with these names. Each student should remember the name of the given animal. The teacher asks each student to make the sound of the named animals and find that group. For example: "me, me..", kittens "meow, meow.." etc.

This method is very convenient and encourages students to expand their thinking, collect a lot of information in a short time, and complete the task by organizing a discussion with each other. In addition to the above tasks, it is also possible to use pictures that embody other tasks. The methodology for organizing music classes is based on the state requirements of the competency approach to education. Minimum requirements for the level of preparation of students during the educational process. The minimum amount of educational content in the subject of the methodology of conducting music lessons. Competencies that should be acquired in music lessons.

Content, essence and analysis of the music education program. The developed program is a state document, which provides for the educational work and training of a music teacher. When planning music lessons, the pedagogue should correctly organize the sequence of the repertoire and types of activities to be taught to the students.

It is envisaged to gradually implement the national values, traditions, folk creativity, musical heritage specific to Uzbeks at the level of students' ability to perceive, while preserving the existing pedagogical tasks. Avalam's music repertoires are divided into quarters, and the materials are aimed at students' perception of qualities such as love for the Motherland, hard work, respect for nature, friendship, solidarity, compassion through musical images education is important in achieving goals. The structure of the lessons should be based on the content of the educational materials. It takes into account the educational value of the works, their artistic and ideological level, suitability for the age of the students, and the variety of the subject of the work.

It is known that musical activity is divided into such types as listening to music, singing, musical rhythmic movement, students learning to play musical instruments. Each type of activity helps to develop the student's musical taste and forms a certain skill.

Pedagogical technology based on didactic improvement and processing of educational material is one of the technologies aimed at updating the content of traditional education and fundamentally changing the organization of the educational process. The design of educational materials based on new pedagogical technology is mainly implemented in the educational process. In this, special attention is paid to ensuring the activity of students and ensuring the assimilation of educational materials.

Pedagogical technology not only organizes the effective relationship between the teacher and students in the educational process, but also ensures the cognitive activity of students. This, in turn, requires the use of not only one technology in the educational process, but the appropriate technology based on its characteristics at each stage of students' learning. Today, in the study of music education, in the design of educational materials, didactic game, problem-based, computer, modular, logical-content, cooperative teaching types of educational technologies are widely used.

How to create a technological map of the lesson depends on the goal set by an experienced teacher. No matter how the technological map is structured, it is important that it reflects the teaching process as a whole, and that a clearly defined goal, task and guaranteed result are expressed. Creating a technological map allows the teacher to write an extended outline of the lesson. Because all aspects of the lesson are reflected in such a map.

The technological map prepared by the teacher for each subject of the subject taught by the teacher allows him to understand how to approach each lesson as a whole, from the beginning of the entire educational process, from the goal, to the result provides an opportunity to organize a lesson. The advanced pedagogical technologies used in the course of the lesson allow students to think freely, creatively approach every issue, to feel responsibility, to work independently, to analyze, to use scientific and methodological literature, textbooks, and most importantly, science. , should strengthen their interest in acquiring knowledge and skills on the subject.

Monitoring students during the lesson is a separate process, and it is carried out in accordance with the purpose and content of each lesson. The most real and correct and effective form of control is self-control. This is necessary for both the teacher and the student. Just as the teaching of each subject has its own characteristics, the music teacher has his own "secrets", that is, his method, his own approach, organization, organization, and the ability to communicate with children. will be Among these, the common features are love for the art of music, one's profession, careful preparation for lessons, giving students more knowledge and

understanding, striving to fully and perfectly master the topics covered. , selflessly, living the life of teaching. A music teacher carries out educational and educational work at the same time. He should not only have extensive knowledge in his specialty, but should also have good knowledge of other subjects related to music, literature, visual arts. A person who educates students musically, artistically, and aesthetically should be of primary importance for his worldview, understanding of thinking, dedication to his profession, and continuous improvement of his skills. In addition, it is good for the teacher to monitor the lessons, record his achievements and shortcomings in a special notebook, and prepare for the next lessons accordingly. Due to constant observations, the pedagogical skills of the teacher grow and develop. He learns to assess the situation, to feel the mood of the students, how the lesson made an impression on them, and their inner feelings. It is desirable that observation be carried out under the principle of "continuity" from the first grade to the seventh grade. In addition, in addition to the use of pedagogical technology, in addition to self-performance, in each lesson, the content, authors, period of creation, genre, character, form, tempo, tone - tonality, should provide the necessary understanding of performance characteristics. In the lesson of music culture, the teacher's vocabulary should be at a high level. The teacher's introduction to the studied piece and the explanation of the subject of the lesson will bring the students into the wonderful and magical world of music. The main basis of such qualities, skills, qualifications are created in the educational process during the period of higher education and are continuously improved, enriched and developed in the teaching activity, which determines the main content of the social order placed before the pedagogues-coaches and their professional activity.

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